

Benchmarking of AM-CM system capabilities to make parts with amorphous and semi-crystalline composites

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Abstract

In this study, we investigated how different types of polymer matrix composites (PMCs), specifically amorphous and semi-crystalline materials, performed in the Additive Manufacturing-Compression Molding (AM-CM) process. Using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), we determine their glass transition temperature (T_g), and crystallization degree. Additionally, An IR camera was used to capture the cooling temperature profile of each PMCs, which were printed on 18 x 12-inch mold to determine cooling profile. Amorphous composites were found to be well-suited for the AM-CM process due to their broad processing window, characterized by a substantial temperature difference between their T_g and printing temperature. This characteristic ensures that the material remains sufficiently pliable during the compression molding stage, facilitating efficient consolidation. In contrast, semi-crystalline materials, especially the high-temperature PMCs, posed challenges due to rapid crystallization. However, certain semi-crystalline composites such as PP/GF, showed promise by retaining heat longer. These findings can pave the way for optimizing the AM-CM system set up to achieve heat retention during the printing stage.

1. Introduction

Thermoplastic polymer matrix composites (PMCs) can be broadly classified into amorphous and semi-crystalline materials based on the matrix type [1]. Amorphous PMCs lack a sharp melting point and exhibit a gradual softening behavior above the glass transition temperature (T_g) [2]. Semi-crystalline PMCs have well-defined melting and crystallization phases, which is associated with rapid solidification.

This study focuses on understanding how the difference in their thermal properties affect their compatibility in the AM-CM process. Through thermal analysis and practical trials, we aim to identify and demonstrate the characteristics that make a PMC compatible with the AMCM process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Table 1 lists the materials employed in this study, including their trade names, manufacturers, and processing temperatures.

Table 1. List of investigated materials in the AM-CM process study

<i>Materials</i>	<i>Designation</i>	<i>Manufacturer</i>	<i>Extrusion temperature (°C)</i>			
			1	2	3	<i>profile</i> Nozzle
<i>Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene reinforced with 20 wt.% carbon fibers composite</i>	ABS/CF	Techmer PM	190	210	230	230
<i>Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene reinforced with 20 wt.% glass fibers composite</i>	ABS/GF	Techmer PM	190	210	230	230
<i>Polyethylene terephthalate glycol with 20 wt.% glass fibers composite</i>	PETG/GF	Techmer PM	245	265	285	285
<i>Polycarbonate with 20 wt.% carbon fibers composite</i>	PC/CF	Techmer PM	250	270	290	290
<i>Polycarbonate with 20 wt.% glass fibers composite</i>	PC/GF	Techmer PM	250	270	290	290
<i>Polypropylene with 30 wt.% glass fibers composite</i>	PP/GF	SABIC	200	220	240	240
<i>Polyphenylene sulfide with 30 wt.% carbon fibers</i>	PPS/CF	Techmer PM	310	330	350	350
<i>Polyaryletherketone with 30 wt.% carbon fibers</i>	PAEK/GF	Victrex	290	310	330	330
<i>Nylon 66 with 40 wt.% carbon fibers</i>	PA66/CF	DowAksa	230	250	270	270
<i>Polyetheretherketone with 30 wt.% glass fibers</i>	PEEK/GF	Victrex	300	320	340	340
<i>Polyetheretherketone with 30 wt.% carbon fibers</i>	PEEK/CF	Techmer PM	340	360	380	380

2.2 Thermal Property Measurement:

Key thermal properties, including glass transition temperature (T_g), and crystallization degree (X_c), were measured using DSC 2500 for both amorphous and semi-crystalline composites. The measurements were conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere with a controlled flow rate of 50 ml/min. Approximately 10 mg pellet samples were subjected to a sequential thermal cycle consisting of heating at 10 °C/min from ambient to 30 °C, holding for 2 minutes, followed by heating to 400 °C, and then cooling at 20 °C/min back to 30 °C. The X_c of the semicrystalline PMCs was determined using Equation 1 based on the enthalpy of melting and cooling peaks.

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{(1 - V_f)\Delta H_m^\circ} \times 100 \quad [1]$$

ΔH_m and ΔH_m° are the actual material enthalpy and enthalpy of the fully crystalline material, respectively and V_f is fiber volume fraction. The enthalpy of the fully crystalline materials was obtained from the literature [3-5].

Cooling profile measurements were conducted to study how these properties influence material behavior during solidification and crystallization. An IR camera was used to capture the cooling temperature profile of each PMC printed on an 18 x 12-inch mold.

3. Results

3.1 Performance of amorphous and semicrystalline composites in the AM-CM process and set up:

The amorphous and semicrystalline PMCs have distinct thermal responses, which reflect as T_g and specific melting temperature, respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1: DSC curves of the investigated PMCs

Amorphous PMCs with glass transition temperature demonstrated excellent compatibility with the AM-CM process. Their gradual softening and absence of a sharp melting point allowed them to flow smoothly during compression molding. The combination of printing and mold temperatures relative to T_g ensured the material remained soft and moldable, facilitating uniform consolidation during the later stage of AM-CM process.

In contrast, high temperature semi-crystalline PMCs, especially those requiring high processing temperatures, posed challenges due to their rapid crystallization rates. This made it difficult to achieve proper fusion during the compression stage.

Interestingly, semi-crystalline materials with high processing temperature above the melting temperature, such as PP/GF, exhibited favorable behavior. These materials retained heat longer, allowing for better flow and controlled crystallization after printing.

The degree of crystallinity of the semicrystalline PMCs are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Degree of crystallinity of the investigated semicrystalline polymer composites.

The cooling profiles of the investigated composites after printing are shown in Figure 3. These experiments were performed using an 18 × 12-inch mold, which required approximately 60 seconds to print a single layer of beads across the surface. The measured times to reach the crystallization temperature (T_c) or glass transition temperature (T_g) provide valuable insight into the compatibility of these PMCs with the AM-CM process.

Figure 3: Cooling profiles of the investigated PMCs.

The cooling time indicated on Figure 3 can be viewed as the window of opportunity available to achieve proper consolidation of the deposited material, considering an additional 30 seconds to shuttle the mold to the press and close it.

These results highlight why PPS/CF was the least compatible material with the AM-CM process. The available consolidation window was extremely limited, as the material solidified

rapidly given the maximum mold temperature achievable with the current setup (200 °C), combined with the added 30-second delay before compression (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Parts produced using different composite materials including amorphous and semicrystalline PMCs on the AMCM.

Moreover, the mold is necessarily maintained below or close to the glass transition temperature, as the part must be removed immediately after the compression molding step. If the material remains above T_g , the part cannot be demolded successfully, making this temperature control an intrinsic aspect of the process. This requirement distinguishes AM-CM from conventional molding processes, where molds can often be heated above the material's T_g or T_m to aid consolidation.

Conclusion

This study shows that amorphous polymer composites are well-suited for the AM-CM process due to their gradual softening and moldable behavior. Semi-crystalline composites, although more challenging, can be optimized through careful material selection and precise thermal management to control heat retention. These findings provide a foundation for advancing AM-CM, with future work focusing on strategies such as optimized toolpathing and heat retention mechanisms to enable the integration of semi-crystalline PMCs.

References

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